

Belonging in the Senegal River Valley: A West African Perspective on Kinship and Integration

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Following the 1989 Senegal-Mauritania conflict, 50,000 black Mauritians were forcibly expelled into the neighbouring state of Senegal. The ethnic and kinship dynamics present in this conflict still impact refugees and migrants today. The varying degrees of ethnic social salience between the two countries have a strong impact on the integration experience of Mauritanian migrants and refugees residing in Senegal. This paper assesses how ethnic groups have experienced integration differently in Senegal and analyses what factors, such as ethnicity, language, and financial status, have influenced their sense of belonging within the Senegalese community. Starting with a history of the conflict and a background on kinship and ethnic research in the region, thematic analysis is performed on qualitative interviews conducted with Mauritanian migrants and refugees who currently reside in Senegal to understand the individual and contextual drivers of integration and belonging. Findings indicate that in the thirty years since the conflict, the main factors influencing integration in Senegal are kinship ties and their influence on language acquisition, disparities in discrimination, and government and administrative sway on refugee acceptance. This study has broad implications for the future of refugee policy in West Africa, as well as for the supposed universality of Western-centric integration frameworks. Scholars and policymakers alike can incorporate lessons about the experience of refugees from different backgrounds living in a neighbouring nation into future literature and recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

In 1989, what started as a conflict over cattle broke out into a brutal ethnic battle that led to the deportation of tens of thousands of black Mauritians. Conflict scholarship and global attention have left this event in the past, but the impact remains felt by the affected population. Revisiting the Senegal-Mauritania conflict and the experiences of the refugees forced into Senegal is now more important than ever, as ethnic and border conflicts rage worldwide and the global refugee population continues to grow. It is essential not only to update the literature on this specific case but also to build a framework of integration that is not based on Western models. The specific social, cultural, political, and socio-economic conditions of non-Western nations must be considered when analysing how an ethnic group has or has not found a new belonging.

While integration theory and kinship studies are robust fields in international relations and sociology, the foundation for most of the scholarship is based on Western Europe (Awad, 2023). Even the field of migration in Africa has largely focused on migration out of the continent and into Europe. Intra-regional migration has received little attention within African studies, but can be examined within Francophone West Africa. Intra-regional migration is defined as “the movement of persons who leave their country of residence to establish themselves either permanently or temporarily in another country belonging to the same region” (Uberti et al, 2015).

This paper will analyse intra-regional migration in West Africa, specifically between Mauritania and Senegal, assessing how ethnic communities and kinship groups enable the integration process for migrants. Existing scholarship acknowledges the role of ethnic networks in integration but does not account for the regional variations and ambiguities in kinship understanding due to the Eurocentricity of the scholarship (Andrikopolous and Duyvendak, 2020). This study will answer the following questions: How do ethnic and kinship ties facilitate a migrant's integration into a new community in non-Western states? How do the specific geospatial, socially hierarchical, and governmental aspects of this region impact integration? Responding to these gaps will help researchers understand how

integration is influenced by specific cultural contexts and adjust integration theory to include cultures outside of Western Europe.

Through a thematic analysis of thirteen interviews conducted in Dakar, Senegal, in the summer of 2024, this analysis will use the specific experiences of Mauritanian migrants and refugees to answer these critical questions. Findings show that ethnicity and kinship play a key role in integration, highlighting the impact of the specific cultural context of the host nation in shaping a migrant's access to their ethnic network. The interviewees indicated that kinship ties were stronger in aiding integration than ethnic ties, going against many Western understandings of social networks, which function hierarchically and emphasise ethnic networks. This underscores the importance of country and region-specific evaluations of kinship and ethnic makeup for the creation of integration frameworks. Furthermore, findings indicate that discrimination is an aspect of integration that requires further analysis, specifically with regard to the interplay between government administration and the refugee or migrant status. Overall, case findings indicate that there is a demand for the restructuring of prevailing Western integration frameworks, as well as a demand to address the physical needs of migrants worsened by the disparity in access provided by kinship networks.

Francophone West Africa, and Senegal specifically, provides a strong case study, as its social situation highlights regional differences in perceptions of ethnicity. The case of Senegal and Mauritania can be applied more broadly to Francophone West Africa as it displays the non-congruent national borders and ethnic borders present throughout the Global South, as well as the ways different cultures affect perceptions of kinship and ethnicity. Current national borders of Francophone West Africa were imposed by French colonial powers from 1895 to 1958, generating national lines that do not align with the long-standing ethnic group lines (Ajayi and Crowder, 1987). When considering the geospatial dimension of kinship and ethnic identity, Africa is unique. To apply the lens of integration to this complicated network presents the opportunity for new findings in a region that has been historically understudied. Understanding the integration factors of the ethnic and geopolitical West African context can help inform frameworks that acknowledge the importance of culturally-specific integration policies. When integration policies are tailored to a specific community, studies indicate that migrants will become better integrated, which diminishes the possibility of in-group versus out-group conflict and strengthens community bonds overall (Ryan, 2011).

Case Study

The Senegal-Mauritania conflict of 1989 can shed valuable light onto the questions of ethnicity and kinship in non-Western regions. This case study will assess: how does the integration process vary between the ethnic groups present in both Senegal and Mauritania? How do migrants use kinship and ethnic ties to integrate into a new community? How does the nature of the ethnic conflict impact integration? By understanding how different groups facilitate integration at the community level, and how that integration looks in cross-group scenarios, one can better understand how ethnicity and perceived in-groupness impact economic, political, social, and cultural integration.

The Senegal-Mauritania Crisis highlights how ethnicity can play a role in both migration and integration for refugees who were expelled during the conflict and new migrants entering Senegal from Mauritania. The crisis started as a farmer-herder conflict that eventually escalated into a full-on ethnic conflict between Arab Mauritians and the black ethnic population of Senegal or Mauritania: the Wolof, Halpulaar, and Soninké. The Mauritanian government saw the border skirmish in the Senegal River Valley as a way to scapegoat the black population of the country. During the conflict, black Mauritians were forcibly expelled into Senegal, on the grounds that they were “actually” Senegalese, despite the majority not being of Senegalese origin (Magistro, 1993). Since 1993, little scholarly research has followed up on the case, and the integration of Wolofs, Halpulaars, and Soninkés into Senegal is a prevalent gap within the literature. All three ethnic groups have a presence in Senegal, the Wolof being Senegal's largest ethnic group with tribal borders that expand into northern Gambia and southwest Mauritania (Sawe, 2017). Wolof is also the most widely spoken language in Senegal, seemingly giving the Wolof ethnic group an integration advantage (Laughlin, 1995).

Of the 50,000 black Mauritians forcibly expelled into Senegal in 1989, around 14,000 refugees still remain and are unlikely to return to Mauritania over fears of political instability, lack of land repatriation, and inability to regain citizenship (UN Refugee Agency, 2009; Thomas-Johnson, 2019).

As Mauritanian migrants from these three ethnic groups continue to move into Senegal, an integration lens can add valuable insight into their community relations. Integration scholarship in Mauritania and Senegal can also be more broadly applied to French-speaking West Africa, given their similar cultural and social contexts. French-speaking West Africa includes Benin, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, and Senegal. These countries have similar colonial histories and political landscapes as a result of historical French colonialism, current neocolonial pressures, and the unique ethnic and geographic makeup of the region. There is value in analysing integration in this region, as varying ethnicities and colonial borders have intersected to create a distinctive cross-group cultural relationship. This, therefore, serves a dual purpose: updating the literature and expanding on the impacts of the Mauritania-Senegal conflict through a multidisciplinary approach.

In relation to migrants moving into Senegal from Mauritania today, this paper will evaluate the strengths of their ethnically-based relationships to see the extent to which their integration process can be mapped onto Western integration frameworks. This paper will assess the differences between kinship and ethnic ties for those integrating into the region, as well as how discrimination and government policy have played a role. Findings from this paper can be used to both inform future government policy and reassess the frameworks scholars use to understand integration, specifically in non-Western settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

To assess the current body of literature, this paper will look at schools of thought in integration theory, kinship and ethnic ties, discrimination, and migration specific to French-speaking West Africa. These theories will help evaluate the framework behind the research and identify gaps in the current literature.

Integration Theory

While the body of literature on integration theory is vast and continuing to adapt, the majority of case studies that inform it are based on Western Europe (Awad, 2023). Although not necessarily pertaining to West Africa, these past studies can provide a strong theoretical framework. For example, in the following definition, Wessendorf and Phillimore observe that “‘integration’ has generally been used in public and academic discourse to refer to processes that entail the socio-economic, political, social and cultural adaptation of newcomers, and the emergence of shared social relations, values, and practices, including, at least in theory, the adaptation of the long-settled population to newcomers” (Wessendorf and Phillimore, 2018). Therefore, an assessment of integration will include socio-economic, political, social, and cultural lenses. These elements show how migrants interact with their community through economic contributions, political engagement, intermarriage, and cross-cultural community engagement. This approach facilitates an assessment of how migrants integrate into a new locality.

The nature of integration theory is multifaceted, without one decidedly agreed-upon definition. Even without a clear definition, practitioners are concerned with how integration can be implemented successfully. One of the factors of successful social integration is social relations and networks (Ryan, 2011). Scholars agree that a focus on enabling migrants to develop social capital will, in turn, lead to a greater sense of belonging (Phillimore, 2012). Senses of belonging and community are foundations of integration research. This concept is defined by McMillan and Chavis as “a feeling that members matter to one another and to the group, and a shared faith that members’ needs will be met through their commitment to be together” (McMillan and Chavis, 1986). Migrants with a strong sense of belonging are more likely to have established social networks which integrate them into the community. Kearns and Whitley argue that the successful factors of implementation are a sense of community, trust and safety, and social relations (Kearns and Whitley, 2015). Having strong social connections strengthens this sense of belonging among migrants, which increases social cohesion.

Ager and Strang provide a theoretical hierarchical framework to assess successful integration (Ager and Strang, 2008). In their work, they use rights and citizenship as the foundation for integration. Ager and Strang also see language, cultural knowledge, and safety and stability as integration facilitators. Social connection is in its own category in Ager and Strang’s framework, which encompasses social bridges, social bonds, and social links. The last section of their framework examines integration markers, including employment, housing, education, and health. Ager and

Strang's framework is a helpful tool to understand mainstream Western integration theory. In politically unstable regions like West Africa, government-given rights are an increasingly challenging process to track. Therefore, it is important to assess how this integration model applies to the situation in Senegal and the ways the theory can potentially be adjusted.

Ager and Stang's framework argues that bonding and bridging are key elements of social connection. Putnam defines bonding as "inward looking [networks that] tend to reinforce exclusive identities and homogeneous groups" and bridging as networks that are "outward looking and encompass people across diverse social cleavages" (Putnam, 2000). Nannestad et al. discuss how bonding and bridging can be used as an approach in migration studies to assess the gains in social capital and their role in the integration process (Nannestad et al., 2008). Strong social networks are indicators of perceived integration into a new region and can increase a migrant's sense of belonging (Wessendorf and Philimore, 2019). Bonding can be seen as weaker integration, as a migrant solely bonds with people they have previous attachments to, whereas bridging is a stronger integration that attaches the migrant to the community as a whole. Ryan argues that when looking at the group cleavages between bridging groups, it is also important to assess the resources that are facilitating these social connections (Ryan, 2011).

With the inherently international nature of integration, a gap in the literature appears, as the theoretical body of knowledge is almost entirely based on Western Europe. Recently, scholars have been calling for research that focuses on other regions, so that these frameworks can be tested in a non-Eurocentric context (Kearns and Whitley, 2015). There has also been a call for more research focused intra-regionally (Uberti et al., 2015). This is especially important considering how the majority of migrants within the Global South migrate intra-regionally (Awad, 2023). This research will bridge the contextual gap between integration theory and its Western roots by generating scholarship in these under-researched regions, specifically Western Africa.

Kinship And Ethnic Ties

Discussions of integration theory are largely predicated on the importance of social networks. As defined by Poros, a "social network is made up of individuals and organisations, often called 'nodes', which are tied together by different sorts of relationships, such as friendship, economic exchange, influence, and common interests" (Poros, 2011). Social networks are an essential feature of migration and integration studies because they often motivate migration and facilitate integration (Ryan, 2011).

Kinship is seen as a building block of the social network (Choldin, 1973). Literature on kinship has evolved since its conception in the 1950s. Initially, kinship was seen as static and descent-based (Andrikopoulos and Duyvendak, 2020). Post-1970s, scholars viewed kinship as dynamic and ethnocentric, reconsidering its potential for evolution due to its basis in perceived identity and community. This is termed by Carsten as 'kinship-as-doing', rather than 'kinship-as-being' (Carsten, 2020). With this progressive view, which will be applied to this study, kinship can be defined as "a set of relationships, practices, ideas, and values that link people in time and space, and whose affective qualities readily attach themselves to particular kinds of objects and material stuff" (Carsten, 2020).

Kinship is generally seen as a strengthener of integration, but, conversely, Ryan presents a different perspective. His paper assesses the strength of kinship ties and the possibility that they might hinder social capital by only allowing migrants to become integrated into their own ethnic groups rather than the larger community as a whole (Ryan, 2011). Kinship exists on a micro level, typically consistent with blood relations, such as parents and siblings, or spouses (Hendrix, 1979). Ethnic ties exist on a macro scale between an ethnic group and can expand out into ethnic networks and resources. Anthias views ethnic ties as essential for facilitating migration and garnering new social capital (Anthias, 2007). She argues that the dichotomy between bonding and bridging is flexible to new migrants, and using ethnic resources is still essential to gaining social capital, which counters Ryan's point. Here, one can see the ways integration theory and kinship studies intersect.

Waterbury views ethnic ties as a building block to the kin-state, an element of diaspora networks and transnational policy-making (Waterbury 2010). A kin-state is defined as "entities that border, or are close to, the region where their kin-groups reside, and they are inhabited by people with whom kin-groups in other states share and maintain strong ethno-cultural and ethno-religious bonds" (Sheffer, n.d.). A gap in the literature appears again here, as the kin-state and the ethnic group are the same in

Waterbury's view. Due to the transnational nature of ethnic groups in Africa caused by the placement of colonial borders, ethnic and kin-state lines are not concentric and do not overlap in the way presented in Western theory.

Andrikopoulos and Duyvendak argue that a specifically ethnic lens is essential to understanding the ambiguities in kinship, especially considering how past definitions of kinship reflected Eurocentric perspectives (Andrikopoulos and Duyvendak, 2020). When looking at kinship research, it is important to note that these studies primarily focus on South-North or North-North migration. The Western conception of kinship might not play out similarly in an African society with its own perception of ethnic ties. For example, Alber et al. discuss how the African notion of kinship was deeply affected and altered by colonialism (Alber et al., 2010). Post-colonialism as a social process of change has affected group structuring and decreased kinship-fosterage, where children are raised with members of the kin-group that are not direct parents, a kinship practice common in Africa that helps strengthen ethnic ties (Alber et al., 2010). Therefore, while there is a body of research concerning kinship in Africa, it has yet to be cross-applied to the migration field in the same way as Western kinship concepts.

Discrimination In Senegal and Mauritania

Understanding Senegal and Mauritania's ethnic backgrounds and their differences is critical for analysing how the two interplay for Mauritanian migrants living in Senegal. While the two countries are neighbours, the way in which ethnic identity has developed in the sixty years since independence has diverged greatly. Differences in government structure and political rights have led to vastly different social situations. The UN Human Rights Committee defines discrimination as "any distinction, exclusion, restriction or preference, which is based on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status, and which has the purpose or effect of nullifying or impairing the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by all persons, on an equal footing, of all rights and freedoms" (Amnesty International, 2021). This definition can be used to assess how the salience of ethnic identity in Senegal and Mauritania has led to ethnic discrimination.

Senegal does not have a particularly salient ethnic political identity, mainly due to a process known as 'Wolofization' (Kuenzi, 2018). In the years since independence, the Wolof language has become the lingua franca of the region, the main language for both Wolof and non-Wolof ethnic groups (Laughlin, 1995). Historically, Senegal has not had a particularly hostile climate across ethnic groups because of the prevalence of 'joking relationships': a way of seeing different groups as separate but related to one's own (Jong, 2005). As the Wolof language spread, the already minimal ethnic division withered further as the main barrier, language, was broken down. Today, Senegal is a multi-ethnic state that is around 43% Wolof, but with prevalent Halpulaar, Jola, Serer, and Soninké communities as well (Sawe, 2017). While these identities are all acknowledged, they rarely impact Senegalese citizens in their day-to-day interactions with neighbours, friends, or co-workers. Religion also serves as a unifying factor along with language, as around 95% percent of Senegalese people are Muslim (Kuenzi, 2018). While discrimination in various forms still exists in Senegal – for instance, on the basis of class and gender – ethnic discrimination is relatively low.

Conversely, ethnicity in Mauritania is incredibly politically salient, as is evidenced by the 1989 conflict that deported black Mauritians along ethnic lines (Jourde, 2001). Thirty years later, ethnicity still impacts economic, social and political interactions. Racially, Mauritania is socially divided into two groups – the 'white' Mauritians, or Hassinya-speaking Arab Maurs, and 'black' Mauritians, predominantly from Halpulaar, Wolof, and Soninké ethnic groups (Jourde, 2001). Ethnic tension between Maurs and black Mauritians persists in the economic and political spheres, as leadership in Mauritania has been consistently Arab, and democratisation has been minimal (Boukhars, 2012). Despite the country being 99% Muslim, religion does not appear to have served as a unifying factor, as the strength of political division far outweighs it (U.S. Department of State, 2023). The asymmetrical power structure has exacerbated cleavages between ethnic groups and subjected black Mauritians to the economic and political whims of their Arab counterparts. Discrimination in hiring and in the buying of property against 'black' Mauritians has been noted as an issue that still persists in Mauritania, along with exclusion from political processes (Boukhars, 2012). For Mauritians, ethnic discrimination is something that greatly impacts their daily life and their ability to be a part of a community.

Discrimination impacts communities in two very different ways in these neighbouring countries, and this difference was compounded by the conflict of 1989. As literature on Mauritanian migrant integration in Senegal has not been recently updated in a scholarly capacity, the question of the role of discrimination as it operates in the current political context needs to be addressed. The continued tense political situation in Mauritania indicates that ethnic tensions likely continue to impact those migrating to Senegal, but the extent of this must be evaluated.

Migration In Francophone West Africa

While integration frameworks have yet to be properly applied to French-speaking West Africa, there is still a body of research concerning the causes of migration in this region. As the vast majority of African migration occurs within the continent, these processes are important to study (Uberti et al., 2015). Looking at West African countries with similar histories of French colonisation (specifically Benin, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, and Senegal) can allow for a broader understanding of factors influencing Mauritanian migrants and refugees. In West Africa, modern causes of intra-regional migration are the labour market, localised conflict, environment, and epidemiological factors (Agadjanian, 2008). Similarly, in the case of Mauritians moving to Senegal, migration is caused by a mixture of localised conflict, with harsh attitudes towards black Mauritians, as well as the labour market, as Senegal presents a hub for work and trade. Understanding the causes of migration will facilitate understanding of the integration process for migrants in Francophone West Africa, specifically the ways ethnic group borders have evolved.

Markets in Francophone West Africa were unable to develop naturally, as they were artificially influenced by French colonial forces, who selected areas they believed would be resource-abundant and set them up as market centres without regard for cultural or environmental factors. Borders in West Africa were similarly drawn by the French, with the Senegal River selected as a border between Senegal and Mauritania due to its potential for trade, in disregard of the ethnic lines that crossed the river (Thomas-Johnson, 2019). In the post-colonial present day, irregular markets continue to cause uneven development, which impacts migration patterns (Agadjanian, 2008). Colonial border politics also affect the irregular movement of migrants. The misalignment of colonial borders and ethnic lines has led to conflicts that result in mass migrations of refugees (Amadife and Warhola, 1993). There is no one hub for migration in West Africa, and economic centres change as conflict and markets develop (Arthur, 1991). Factors such as uneven development, mass expulsions, and unstable labour markets have led to continued irregular migration patterns as foci are still evolving (Dinbabo and Badewa, 2020). African ethnic groups traditionally moved across borders freely, and the imposition of and continued maintenance of colonial perimeters have influenced perceived ethnic identity and the kin-state during post-colonial statehood. (Aning and Pokoo, 2017; Amadife and Warhola, 1993).

To conclude, the way borders were developed and influence migration in West Africa vastly differs from migration around Western Europe. Colonial history, Africa's uneven development, and migration patterns have led to different interpretations of social networks caused by Africa's shifting kin-state and misaligned ethnic and national borders. Conflict is greatly interconnected with migration in West Africa, which necessitates a greater level of nuance when analysing migrant integration. Perceptions of kinship and ethnic ties are also bent through the lens of post-colonialism and the fairly new notion of the State on imagined communities in West Africa.

Gaps In The Literature And Contribution

When analysing the outlined schools of thought, it is clear that the gaps in the literature intersect. Integration theory lacks an international perspective, as it is firmly centred in Western Europe's notion of 'belonging,' which displays ethnic networks as being a key driver for social integration. Kinship studies encompass scholarship in Africa and scholarship concerning migration, but those two fields have yet to interact. When scholars research the intersection between kinship and migration, the standard is to observe these patterns within Western Europe, which limits the universality of their findings and eliminates most regions that do not simulate European development and culture. Senegal and Mauritania have distinct experiences with ethnic salience and racial discrimination, but the ways the two interact for migrants have not been addressed. Lastly, little research has been conducted concerning migrant integration in Francophone West Africa, specifically intra-regionally, leaving wide gaps in the scholarly literature.

This paper seeks to contribute to the scholarship in all four schools by studying the intersection of ethnicity and migration in Senegal. This theoretical question will close important gaps concerning how African-specific kinship and ethnic group dynamics create and compound social networks and whether they enable or hinder integration. Not only will this contribute to the internationalisation of integration and kinship research, but it could also help inform African-specific integration policy.

METHODOLOGY

Research Method

Using an epistemologically interpretivist approach – and sensitive to the ethnographic nature of this study – I conducted qualitative interviews from May to July of 2024. An interpretivist approach suits the previous scholarly assumptions in integration research, which are based on the social constructs and perceived reality that can change based on the individual. Furthermore, the research aims not to explain why people integrate but to understand how integration can rely on kinship ties and how that affects the process. This approach fits well with the data collection method, an interactive and collaborative process of semi-structured interviews. This study seeks to understand and interpret individuals' experiences of integration within a specific cultural context.

Data Collection

The interviews were semi-structured with Mauritanian migrants and refugees living in Dakar. Interview questions were divided into three sections: 1) Demographic Questions, 2) Life in Senegal, and 3) Identity. Questions were based on the integration frameworks presented in the literature review, specifically the 'bonding-bridging' perspective. Each interviewee was asked the same basic set of questions, but the nature of the semi-structured interviews led to varied follow-up questions. Interviews were conducted in both French and Wolof, with the help of a translator for the Wolof interviews. French is the national language of Senegal, while Wolof is the 'langue maternelle', or mother tongue, of the region. Most educated people in Dakar speak French, but in the case of some migrants and refugees, only Wolof is spoken, and is often a second language on top of Peul (Fulani) or Hassaniya (Mauritanian Arabic). I interviewed thirteen people, with ten of the thirteen interviews recorded to ensure they were translated and transcribed correctly. Of the three interviewees who declined to be recorded, analysis was done based on notes from the interview. All interviews were eventually translated into English for content analysis.

These interviews were set up via three distinct avenues. The first was through word of mouth, where I asked colleagues at Cheikh Anta Diop University if they had any friends or colleagues who were Mauritanian. I was able to set up four interviews this way, all of which were in French. The next avenue I used to garner interviews was by walking around in a Mauritanian enclave in Dakar (the neighbourhood of Medina) and asking if people wanted to be interviewed. There was more hesitation with this method, though I was able to achieve four interviews, all of which were with migrants, three of whom only spoke Wolof. Lastly, I was able to set up five interviews with the United Nations High Commission on Refugees' office in Dakar, the Green Village Foundation. These interviewees were entirely refugees, with three interviews occurring in French and two in Wolof with translator assistance.

The interview sample showed a varied view of Mauritanian life in Dakar. It consisted of eleven men and two women, six of whom were refugees and seven of whom were migrants. Refugees are those who had migrated in 1989 as a result of the conflict, and migrants are anyone who migrated for non-conflict-related reasons in the thirty years since. All interviewees were either employed or students, of which there were three. They worked in a number of fields, from professors to housekeepers to nurses. Ages ranged from 18 to 65, with each range fairly evenly represented. Racially, they were very diverse, with four Maurish people, or "white" Mauritians. There was one Wolof, one Soninké, and seven Halpulaar, all of whom are considered "black" Mauritians. Through this sample, important lessons can still be learned, specifically in a comparison between refugee and migrant experiences and the experience of urban integration. For further demographic details of interviewees, see the appendix.

DATA ANALYSIS

After interviewing, I used thematic analysis to systematise the data through the Nvivo programme. Thematic analysis is a qualitative process of analysis that involves closely examining a text to pull out specific themes and patterns that occur within it. This approach analysed specific themes in the migrant's narratives, as the interviews were coded for conflict, discrimination, financial difficulties,

government relations, impact of language, kinship ties, ethnic ties, positive integration/sense of belonging, perceptions of negative integration, separation from Mauritania, closeness to Mauritania, and proposed solutions. As this study uses an interpretivist approach, there is no one 'answer' to find within the research, but instead a relativist interpretation of relationships.

Thematic analysis allowed for the running of tests on the frequency with which migrants discussed certain issues, as well as drawing inferences from the relationships between different coded sections and selecting pertinent quotes. As the sample size was relatively small, the goal in analysing interviews was not to make broad generalisations, but instead to understand how each individual's experience impacted their relationship to integration. This is especially important with the semi-structured nature of the interviews, which invited fluidity into the conversations.

Ethics And Limitations

Ethical considerations are critical in this field research, specifically concerning the interview stage of the process. With the language barrier, ensuring informed consent was essential. I presented the right to refuse to answer a question or leave at any time during the interview. It was also essential to clarify intentions and explain that I am a researcher funded by a university, and that the interviewees would remain anonymous after the interview if the findings are published. There were various levels of understanding of the purpose of the research – mainly due to a more difficult language barrier with Wolof-only participants. Interviews where the translator said it was harder to communicate the purpose of the research had a much higher rate of interviewees declining to answer certain questions, specifically those surrounding the conflict.

This study has several limitations, the first being location. The interviews were all conducted in the capital city of Dakar, which has a large population of migrants. While Dakar is a migrant hub and the centre of culture and commerce in Senegal, there are many Mauritanian migrants who still live in communities close to the Senegal River Valley. Because of this, these interviews were only able to gain an urban perspective on integration in Senegal, rather than a rural one, which likely also meant participants were of a relatively higher socio-economic class. Secondly, the sample size skewed largely towards the Halpulaar ethnic group, which weakens the ethnic comparison being made. While this does not discount the stories and experiences of the migrants interviewed, there is still room for further research with larger sample sizes from the Wolof and Soninké ethnic groups.

There were also limitations concerning language. Eight out of the thirteen interviews were conducted in French, a language that I speak. Of the five interviews that were conducted in Wolof, three were with a translator who was more unfamiliar with the research, and two were with a translator who had also helped with the French interviews and transcribing. These Wolof interviews varied in quality and detail of response because of the methods and familiarity of these two translators. Lastly, there were also limitations on who I was able to speak with, as relates to the three methods of finding interviewees. These sources were word of mouth/friends of professional colleagues, merchants in Mauritanian neighbourhoods, and those connected with the UNHCR. Therefore, certain socio-economic and social classes were not reached. For example, the interviewees were skewed toward academics, as many of the people helping me find interviewees were professors in Dakar. While not discrediting the interviews performed, this does limit the scope of the research in whose voices were able to be heard. A future study concerning the rural and lower economic class migrants and refugees in Senegal would fill these gaps.

FINDINGS

A review of the interviews shows new insights in three key areas: (1) kinship and ethnic ties, (2) discrimination and its relationship to integration, and (3) the impact of government policy on refugees and migrants. This section will discuss in depth the conclusions and how they reflect the larger integration process for Mauritanians moving to Senegal.

Kinship Ties Versus Ethnic Ties

Kinship Ties: Kinship ties describe the fluid connection a migrant has with close relations such as, but not limited to, members of their immediate family, extended family, and other members of the ethnic group that they personally know and have a connection with. Kinship is a building block of the larger social and ethnic networks.

Ethnic Ties: Ethnic ties exist on a larger scale than kinship ties, constituting the bonds between anyone within a larger ethnic group, whether directly related or not.

Through the process of interviewing, kinship and ethnic ties presented themselves in ways that were not concurrent with the bonding-bridging dichotomy and other Western integration frameworks. In the specific case of Senegal, ethnicity had a relatively low effect on integration, and ethnic ties were not especially potent. This is caused by the minimal ethnic visibility due to homogeneity in physical appearance and language. Wolofization – the encompassing usage of the Wolof language and the way it blurs with ethnic understanding – allowed for social integration to surpass the strict lines of ethnicity. Lastly, the ways in which kinship ties grounded and stabilised migrant experiences did seem to have a larger effect than what was indicated from the integration frameworks, specifically with regard to pathways for language acquisition.

Members of different ethnic groups did not strongly differ in their feelings of integration. Race and ethnicity overlap in interesting ways in Senegal; therefore, black Mauritians and Senegalese see each other as “the same people,” a phrase that was repeated often in the interviews. This is different from how they see Hassaniya people, or “white” Mauritians. This social division seemed far more pertinent than that of ethnicity between black groups, despite the social and cultural salience of these various ethnic groups. Black Mauritanian and Senegalese ethnic groups have a more fluid perception of their ethnicity, and this was reflected in their integration experiences (Laughlin, 1995). While the sample size was relatively small, I still expected to see differences in how the ethnic groups related to the larger communities around them based on the group's establishment. This was not the case, as across interviews there was a general sentiment that ethnic groups had not played a large role, both in creating an environment of belonging and informing migrants of social practices. Socially, interviewees did not seem to organise themselves along ethnic lines.

A likely reason why ethnic group division does not play a large role in the feeling of integration is due to the similarity in physical appearance between the Halpulaar, Wolof, and Soninké ethnic groups. There was minimal correlation between one's ethnic group and the likelihood of feeling integrated, and when interviewees said they did not feel integrated, there was usually a specific reason unrelated to their ethnic group. Physical appearance was important to feeling integrated in Senegal, with interviewees describing their similarities to black Senegalese citizens as grounding. Several interviewees described how they could “pass” in Senegal, as there are no easily identifiable traits between ethnic groups. A 62-year-old Halpulaar refugee described how this helped him easily integrate with the community in Senegal, as he was not immediately othered like he was in Mauritania, “And if I don't say I'm of Mauritanian origin, no Senegalese can know I'm of Mauritanian origin. I pass” (Interview Two). The similarities in ethnic group appearance have made belonging to an ethnic group negligible in integration, especially with the more tolerant and friendly relationships Senegalese ethnic groups historically have (Jong, 2005). A 49-year-old Soninké migrant discussed how easy it was for him and other migrants to blend in: “When it's black Mauritians from the valley who are Wolof, Soninké or Fulani who settle in Senegal, frankly, if they don't emphasise their Mauritanian identity, no one will know that they're Mauritanian” (Interview Four).

Language was more relevant than ethnic ties for perceived integration. Wolof is the most widely spoken language in Senegal, and one does not have to belong to the Wolof ethnic group in order to access this form of social and in-group integration. Seven interviewees cited knowing Wolof as an important factor in their sense of belonging to the Senegalese community. Prior to the French colonisation of Senegal, different ethnic groups had fewer interactions within the region and mostly spoke their own indigenous language. With the imposition of French colonial powers, the Wolof language dominated in the trade sector, and then grew into a general lingua franca (Laughlin, 1995). Post-independence, French is spoken as the language of commerce and academics, but Wolof still holds the place of the langue maternelle or mother tongue. Almost all Senegalese people speak Wolof, even if it is not the language of their ethnic group. Wolofization has contributed to a shift in the perceptions of ethnic identity, as Senegalese identity has become blurred with the Wolof identity. This has led to the incorporation of other traditionally Senegalese ethnicities into the Wolof identity, specifically in urban areas (Laughlin, 1995).

Therefore, despite the multiethnic citizenry, there is really only one language a migrant needs to learn to access the social aspects of Senegalese life. This is a relatively low barrier to entry and is not

predicated on a specific ethnic group, but rather one's ability to learn the Wolof language, which interviewees reported was not particularly difficult. When asked what made him feel integrated, a mixed Hassaniya and Halpulaar student responded, "First of all, I speak Wolof well" (Interview Three). When asked about the difficulties of integrating into Senegal, the 49-year-old Soninké migrant stated, "The only difficulty is that my knowledge of the Wolof language is very approximate and limited" (Interview Four). When asked about barriers to integration, a thirty-two-year-old Hassaniyan migrant offered, "For me [the difficulty] is partly because I haven't yet learned Wolof" (Interview Seven). More than any specific ethnic claim, language seemed to be a primary integrator for people, and once obtained, an easy way to facilitate social interaction in Senegalese society.

While ethnic ties did not seem to have an effect on how a migrant integrated, kinship ties did. Out of migrants who stated they felt well integrated, 60% cited their family as a facilitator of their integration. For many migrants, this meant that they had cousins, or some other relation, who had been in Senegal previously and whom they were able to connect with. When asked what helped his integration, the student migrant answered, "Well, it's all because I have family who live here in Senegal" (Interview Three). For others, it simply meant having built a family in Senegal, such as marrying someone who was Senegalese or having children integrated into the Senegalese school system, which made them feel grounded in the larger community. As a Wolof migrant stated when asked if he felt integrated into Senegal, "I thrive with my family. The people are nice, the population is nice" (Interview One).

To tie back to the earlier discussion on language, migrants also stated that having family helped them learn Wolof more easily, and therefore, integrate into Senegalese culture. The student said, "And since [my cousins] all spoke Wolof, I had to speak Wolof because sometimes in the neighbourhoods, there aren't too many people who speak French. So we all speak Wolof" (Interview Three). This example shows how kin relationships can actively play a role in one's integration in a stronger way than simple camaraderie. Having familial ties present not only allowed one to feel less alone, but they also offered pathways into integration through language learning and social stability.

Discrimination Dimension

Despite going unmentioned in the majority of integration frameworks, racial discrimination played a large role in the interviewees' sense of belonging. Specifically, discrimination experienced in Mauritania allowed Mauritanian migrants to feel closer to the Senegalese community. This was further reinforced by the deterioration of international diplomatic relations with Mauritania due to racial discrimination and complicated migrants' perspectives on their home country.

Discrimination in Mauritania was brought up in seven of the thirteen interviews, across all ethnic groups, despite there being no questions directly related to it. Interviewees asserted that their past discriminatory experiences led them to feel a sense of belonging and gratitude for Senegalese communities, which respected their identities and did not reinforce a racial hierarchy. When asked what made him feel integrated, a 49-year-old Wolof migrant responded, "I think it's enough to be treated better than in your own country" (Interview One). Experiencing a community void of a racial hierarchy was gratifying after coming from Mauritania, where interviewees experienced forced deportation and racialised violence. The Wolof migrant continued, "So in Mauritania, for example, you'll find a neighbourhood that favours whites and Arabs, and another that favours one ethnic group or another. In Senegal, there's no such discrimination. You have to have the means to live in a neighbourhood without financial discrimination whatsoever" (Interview One).

This was further exemplified through, as three interviewees cited, their ability to "pass," or blend in with Senegalese society without notice. As the Soninké migrant discussed, "In any case, for me in Senegal, if I don't say I'm Mauritanian, nobody can know I'm Mauritanian" (Interview Four). This ties into the early conversations about ethnic groups, and the inability to discern between the in-group and the other. For migrants coming into this community, after being in one that was highly racialised, they felt a sense of relief. Senegal was a place where interviewees said that they could finally exist without the confines of a racist governmental and societal institution.

Interviewees also discussed how discrimination has continued to hurt migrants internationally and damage diplomatic efforts between the two nations. As a 45-year-old Halpulaar refugee described, "If it wasn't for the racism of white Mauritians, the relationship between the bordering countries would be fine" (Interview Ten). Interviewee Thirteen, another Halpulaar refugee, seconded this perspective,

and discussed how Mauritania's continued denial of its crimes against black Mauritians has hurt him and any possible ties he has to his home country. More than thirty years later, the continued racism and ethnic classifications by the government created a further separation between migrants and their country of origin.

Discrimination in Mauritania was therefore cited as a reason for migrants not wanting to return to their home country. Of the seven interviewees who responded that they were not planning on returning to Mauritania, five brought up racism and struggles with the Mauritanian government as a reason not to return.

Conversely, the discrimination faced in Mauritania was, for one refugee, the reason he did not want to accept Senegalese citizenship. Interviewee Twelve felt as if accepting a place within Senegalese society was conceding that the Mauritanian government had been correct in their expulsion of black citizens, where they had stated that these citizens were 'actually' Senegalese (Magistro, 1993). When asked if he had considered taking Senegalese nationality, he responded, "If I didn't want it, I have my reasons. We were chased out of the country to say that we are Senegalese. And if we agree today to take the Senegalese nationality, we'll be giving these racists reason" (Interview Twelve). This nuanced perspective highlights the complicated nature of ethnic-based displacement, and the placelessness that these migrants and refugees continue to feel today, thirty years after the conflict ended.

Government: Refugee Versus Migrant

Government attitudes towards refugees were deeply influential in how refugees felt integrated into their communities. According to the interviewees, in 2023, the Senegalese government did not renew refugee cards, leaving refugees of the 1989 crisis in a legal grey zone. Both on a tangible level and on a social and subconscious level, the question of status has challenged belonging and exacerbated existing inequalities between refugees and migrants. The lack of government assistance further emphasised the need for kinship ties and the importance of family connections in social and professional stability.

In comparing the experiences of migrants and refugees, there is a skew towards migrants feeling more integrated than refugees. Out of six refugees, only three said they felt integrated into the Senegalese community, whereas all seven migrants said they felt integrated. This was interesting when considering the time factor, as the refugees had all been in the country since the early 90s, and every interviewed migrant had moved to Senegal post-2000, many within the past decade.

Of the refugees who said they did not feel integrated, the government seemed to be a large factor. There was mention in interviews of not feeling accepted by the Senegalese community, as well as the poor financial situation in Senegal. However, the most common thread was the way refugees felt mistreated by the Senegalese government. Where migrants claimed they had an easy time accessing social services in Dakar, it seemed to be much more difficult for refugees, with both money, connections, and status as a barrier. The administration did not appear to have a clear answer on whether refugees had the legal standing to stay in the country. Refugees indicated that their acceptance by the Senegalese population was somewhat predicated on it not being immediately obvious that they had come from Mauritania, and once their legal status came into question, treatment changed.

Even some Mauritanian migrants lacked sympathy for the refugees in Senegal. A Wolof migrant who moved to Senegal for work in 2010 stated, "I don't have any particular difficulties with the Senegalese government because I think that to have difficulties, you have to do something that goes against the country, against the authorities" (Interview One). This was not the experience of refugees, who often found themselves in conflict with police who questioned their documentation. A Halpulaaran refugee discussed this, "Sometimes it's difficult. Sometimes we show our refugee cards, and they say they don't recognise it" (Interview Ten). Another refugee echoed this sentiment, "Yes, it's not easy because the refugee card we have here in Senegal is 95% useless, because even if you take this out into the street, it's not even recognised. Because to have access to the Senegalese population, the validity of the card must be important, either in the police or in security" (Interview Eleven).

The non-renewal of the refugee cards has taken away the Mauritanian refugees' legal status, meaning they cannot legally leave the country. The uncertainty of their future left refugees anxious and

confused about where they belonged in Senegalese society. A 63-year-old Halpulaar refugee discussed this feeling, “We don't have a problem with the Senegalese population. Our problems are all with the government, the Senegalese government. They left us stranded” (Interview Twelve). He then explained the difficulties surrounding the refugee cards, “They started making us cards, identity cards, refugee cards. If we send you a card, we tell you it's not valid. And it's signed by the Ministry of the Interior. And where I'm talking to you now, where we've been, we're clueless, we don't have any papers, all the papers have expired. All papers have expired. This expired in 2023” (Interview Twelve).

Financial difficulties also seem to be a large part of the issues with the government. Certain government resources, such as scholarships, are unavailable to people who are not of Senegalese origin, even if they have been naturalised, a restriction that applies to both migrants and refugees. The migrants and refugees with the most successful integrations, both socially and otherwise, appeared to be those who already had family across the border, and could use familial resources, such as a house to live in, to facilitate integration. Given that Senegalese society is very family-oriented in terms of living and social life, to be without this connection meant there was another hurdle to overcome in terms of finding one's place in Senegal. Having the security network provided by kinship ties also meant that refugees and migrants could afford the time and risk of making connections within the broader Senegalese community.

Regarding their professional lives, the government made it difficult for refugees to purchase land for agriculture, which ironically ties back to the catalyst of the Senegal-Mauritania conflict: a land dispute. A Halpulaar refugee discussed this difficulty, “It's a problem because those who have taken refuge here need land to grow crops. And land is not privileged for refugees, because we're foreigners here” (Interview Thirteen). Furthermore, a Wolof migrant discussed how finding a job is generally harder in Senegal, as he and other migrants like him don't have access to their local social networks, “Life is much easier financially in Mauritania because when you're in Mauritania, there's a lot more knowledge, so it's easier to get a job somewhere. But in Senegal, when you're there, you don't know many people” (Interviewee One). There is a clear need for government assistance in finding jobs and opportunities for both migrants and refugees. However, it would appear that the government is actively making it more difficult for Mauritians to secure employment in Senegal, or at least putting up a high barrier to entry. Further research on the perceptions of the receiving society, in this case, Senegalese perspectives on Mauritanian migrants, might further illuminate why the Senegalese government has left Mauritanian migrants politically isolated.

The government's actions, or rather, lack of action, exacerbated existing barriers for Mauritanians moving into Senegal, mainly in the financial sense. While most migrants and refugees claimed they were easily able to integrate into the Senegal community, there still appeared to be deeper professional, political, and societal issues.

CONCLUSION

The findings of my interviews have both answered integration questions and revealed further gaps that must be addressed. In highlighting the position of Mauritanian migrants and refugees in Senegal, this paper has shown that the experiences of interviewees do not align with Western integration frameworks. New frameworks – whether updated versions of the current models, or new regionally-specific versions – are required for the future of integration theory. On a material level, further support is required for Mauritanians residing in Senegal. To return to integration theory, an assessment of integration includes cultural, social, political, and socio-economic lenses. This framework will be used to place findings within the larger context of integration research.

Culturally, it is important to understand the different ways that ethnicity is interpreted in a Francophone West African context. In Senegal, the process of Wolofization lowered the salience of ethnic identity, which led to ethnic ties being de-emphasised compared to direct kinship ties. Relative to Mauritania, where ethnicity is central to the social hierarchy, it is clear that this region is not a monolith when it comes to perceptions of ethnicity, even though the two countries have similar ethnic groups. As Andrikopoulos and Duyvendak (2020) indicate, scholars must consider both the cultural and the national contexts when understanding how a group might integrate into a new country. Despite the similar ethnic groups, family and language served as far bigger factors of integration in the Senegalese context, contrary to what many Western integration models might suggest. The case

of Wolofization also indicated the fluidity of interpretations of ethnicity, another dimension of integration deserving of its own study.

Socially, one can return to the bonding and bridging framework. While this study approached the data with the intention of using this framework to assess the salience of migrant integration, it proved inadequate when applied to the Senegalese-Mauritanian context. The different conceptions of ethnicity present in Senegal led to difficulty in determining what relationships constituted as bonding and which were bridging. Almost every migrant said they had relationships with the larger Senegalese community and, within that, people from all ethnic groups. The only group that seemed not to have larger Senegalese community connections was the Maurish or “white” Mauritians interviewed, which might indicate that the split is along the lines of perceived ethnicity. Within the Wolof, Halpulaar, and Soninké groups, bridging seemed an ineffective way to assess their connections with the community. There is room to develop a different integration framework that better speaks to this ethnic context. That being said, the sample size also skewed towards the Halpulaar ethnic group, so future studies that include larger numbers of Wolof and Soninké members might be able to better indicate the specific differences in perceived ethnicity between these groups.

Politically, one can return to the Ager and Strang framework, which postulates that rights and citizenship are the basis for integration. As refugee interviewees shared, this ‘foundation’ of citizenship has never truly been cemented for them, due to the lack of renewal on their refugee cards. While refugees were still able to integrate to some capacity despite their fluctuating status, this political hindrance affects their perception of identity within the Senegalese context. One might classify refugees in Senegal as socially but not politically integrated, a classification that should be studied further alongside their refugee status, as this study was unable to find any articles indicating the lack of renewal, and only learned about it after physically seeing the expired cards. These legal and political nuances exist throughout West Africa, and while originally this study originally assumed that because they are regionally common, they would have minimal effect on integration, that was incorrect. The inconsistencies with the Senegalese government affected large parts of refugees’ day-to-day lives – from interactions with security and administration forces to the government programmes they were allowed to use. The hierarchical integration model falls apart when examining how these factors apply to Mauritanian migrants, who do not have the ‘foundation’ for integration, yet still find places where they belong and are socially integrated. Furthermore, discrimination affects Mauritanian migrant integration, yet was not highlighted in any Western integration models. If in the future a non-Western centric integration model is developed, this paper recommends that it focus in part on the impacts of discrimination.

Socio-economic factors also played an especially important role in each interviewee’s experience of integration. Simply put, access to money, jobs, and general financial stability made it infinitely easier to make connections within a new country. This is what made kinship ties so important; the ways in which kinship operates in West African society means it could become a pathway to these socio-economic factors. Socio-economic stability is a factor of integration that is rarely highlighted in integration scholarship, which is a detriment when it comes to creating policies that support migrants. If the purpose of developing integration frameworks is to support governments and NGOs that provide resources to support migrants, financial stability is fundamental. Basic needs must be prioritised for a sense of belonging to be facilitated. In this case study, kinship ties provided stability in terms of housing and connections that are a gateway to other forms of integration. Kinship ties cannot be replicated for those without them, so in their place, strong government, policy, and humanitarian aid are needed.

To conclude, this research exposes the gaps and fissures in the Western integration model. The kinship and geospatial aspects of ethnic identity in Senegal differ from what is seen in Western states, which leaves the Western frameworks inadequate in this setting. On a theoretical level, further research is needed to assess what a Francophone West African model of integration would look like, highlighting how financial, political, and ethnic factors play unique contextual roles. On a tangible level, it is clear that more attention needs to be provided to the refugees and migrants in Senegal. Pressure must be applied to the Senegalese government to renew the refugee cards and solidify their legal status, a topic that has not been reported on in Western media. Moreover, programmes such as Wolof language classes, job training, and direct financial support will likely positively impact Mauritians living in Senegal. For those without the advantage of family and strong kinship ties,

achieving financial, professional, and social stability is the next step to integrating the Senegalese community.

Zoe Carver

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APPENDIX

Interview	Status	Ethnicity	Language/ Audio Status	Age	Profession	Gender	Year Migrated
1	Migrant	Wolof	Recorded in French	45-60	IT Specialist	Male	2010
2	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in French	60+	Professor	Male	1989
3	Migrant	Halpulaar/Hassaniya	Recorded in French	18-30	Student	Male	2014
4	Migrant	Soninké	Recorded in French	45-60	Professor	Male	2020
5	Migrant	Hassaniya	Not recorded in Wolof	30-45	Merchant	Male	2008
6	Migrant	Hassaniya	Not recorded in Wolof	30-45	Merchant	Male	2022
7	Migrant	Hassaniya	Recorded in French	30-45	Student	Male	2024
8	Migrant	Hassaniya	Not recorded in Wolof	30-45	Merchant	Male	2023
9	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in Wolof	45-60	House cleaner	Female	1989
10	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in Wolof	45-60	House cleaner	Female	1989
11	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in French	18-30	Student	Male	Born 1995 to refugees
12	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in French	60+	Nurse	Male	1989
13	Refugee	Halpulaar	Recorded in French	60+	Administrator	Male	1989